

FOOD SECURITY SUPPLY PROSPECTS

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Abstract: One of the important needs of people is the need for food products. This requires the increase of this type of products. Agriculture is one of the important sectors in food production.

Key words: Food, small business, entrepreneurship, import, export, foreign economy, investment, innovation

INTRODUCTION

It is no secret that thousands and thousands of people in the world suffer from various diseases and die prematurely due to hunger. According to the information of authoritative international organizations, at present, more than 1 billion people on the globe do not have enough bread.

Decree of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure reliable protection of private property, small business and private entrepreneurship, and to eliminate obstacles to their rapid development" adopted on May 15, 2015 to radically increase the role and place of private entrepreneurship in the economy, to eliminate existing obstacles and restrictions on the way to organize entrepreneurial activities, including creating more favorable economic and legal conditions and incentives for producers of agricultural products focused.

According to the data, in the last 35 years of the world's population to wheat the demand has doubled, and the amount of grain production is six hundred million reached tons. At present, wheat compared to the area of all cereal crops the cultivated land area is 32 percent of the world. Specialists According to him, the demand for wheat will increase by 40% in the next 20-25 years. So, in 2020, the world's need for wheat will be 840 million tons organize is enough. This is it demand satisfy for the world according to wheat it is necessary to increase the yield almost twice as much as it is today is enough. From this apparently in the future in the world food shortage the problem solution reach very tight from issues one being is considered

Our country of independence initial since days village economy Large-scale reforms were launched in the field and grain independence idea forward pushed. Of grain advanced methods, modern and intensive agro-technologies were boldly put into

practice and the harvest from abroad was rapidly dead without doing harvest will receive combine harvesters buy received. also farmers material interest to increase separately attention given As a result Uzbekistan grain independence intermittently achieved

I A Karimov, the first president of our country, in 2015 results of socio-economic development and economic for 2016 of the program the most important priority directions dedicated Ministers Court extended meeting in his lecture as noted:

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Deep changes are being implemented in the economy of our Complicated the weather conditions regardless farmer and of our farmers unselfishly work and efficiency because of past year plenty harvest was cultivated 7 million 500 a thousand from the ton more than grain, 3 million 350 a thousand more than a ton cotton threshing floor set up It should be noted that such an abundant harvest is mainly produced in agriculture acceleration of production, improvement of selection works, cotton and grain crops zoned varieties current to do modern agricultural technologies in return for appropriation provided.

The average yield of wheat per hectare in our country is 55 quintals, There is no doubt that in some districts this figure was 60-77 centners. of our farmers huge is an achievement. This while own in turn, again working enterprises raw material, population while food products with full to provide also village economy products export potential created the basis for the increase. Most importantly, in the short term, our country's food food safety provided.

Ensuring food security from available resources in the region based on scientific and technical achievements through efficient and rational use, population food products has been needs satisfy means also food of products sanitation, veterinary medicine, phytosanitary norms and compliance with the rules understood.

Our country population high quality, safe, vitamins and mineral providing nutrient-rich food products is one of the priorities defined as Because food products contain vitamins and minerals lack of substances, morbidity and mortality among mothers and children increase, children and of teenagers intellectual-physical development due to the decrease, and the work abilities of older people decrease will come. This is the only safe and cost-effective way to prevent negative consequences food products content is enrichment.

Our state's policy is primarily to enrich the population with food products to provide directed social, economic, legal, organizational measures done increase and food products enrichment for vitamin-mineral of mixtures quality and safety over state control provide important task is considered

Above as we noted population food products withto provide exactly village economy network in charge of the fact that to us known. Thisbecause the industry occupies an important place in the socio-economic life of our republic in agriculture from the first years of independence under the leadership of our country's president wide scope reforms done increased. In particular, economy of keeping the most efficient, progressive reached countries in experience himself each bilaterally justified farming to the movement passing this field in development new period starting from gave

As the first president of our country, Islam Karimov, noted, thanks to the implemented measures, the production of agricultural products doubled during the years of independence. Despite the fact that the population of our country has increased by almost 10 million people or more than 30 percent, the per capita consumption of meat has increased by 1.3 times, milk and milk products by 1.7 times, vegetables by 2 times, fruits by almost A 4-fold increase was achieved.

Due to the structural changes in the agrarian sector, industries such as fruit and vegetable growing, horticulture, viticulture and animal husbandry are increasingly developing. As a result, in 2019, 12 million 592 thousand tons of vegetables and potatoes, 1 million 850 thousand tons of vegetable products, 1 million 556 thousand tons of grapes, 2 million 731 thousand tons of fruits were grown. This is about 300 kilograms of vegetables, 75 kilograms of potatoes and 44 kilograms of grapes per capita. This means that it is three times more than the optimal, that is, acceptable standard of consumption.

From this it seems that Uzbekistan not only internal food safety but also provides food to foreign countries to the market of products worthy contribution is adding.

In 2015, our country became the United Nations Food and village economy organization to (FAO). a member has been of states food safety provide in the field Millennium development goals achievedrecognition as one of the 14 countries to receive the award for done.

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Today, food, with a total value of almost 5 billion dollars, is being exported, first of all, fruit and vegetable products. In the next three years, the amount of exported agricultural products increased more than 3 times. As a result, 180 types of quality fruits and vegetables and products made on the basis of their processing are being exported to more than 80 countries of the world. Our country ranks among the leading countries in the export of apricots, walnuts, plums, grapes, cabbage and many other fruit and vegetable products.

During the years of independence, the growth rate of food production increased by 8-10% every year, and the needs of the domestic market are met mainly at the expense of domestically produced products. In 2018-2020, a total of 312 fruit-vegetable, meat and dairy processing enterprises were established in order to ensure food safety and provide continuous and sufficient food products for the population's consumption. Including construction of 169 new enterprises and reconstruction and modernization of 143 existing enterprises. As a result of ensuring their implementation, 63.1 thousand tons of fruits and vegetables, 16.5 thousand tons of meat, 45.7 thousand tons of dairy products processing facilities were established in our country.

Village economy in the field done being increased reforms and structural changes more deepening, land and water resources efficient It is important to use economic programs for 2019 and the near future is the direction.

Country food safety of provision main mechanisms

Organizational mechanisms - extraordinary situations population food development of a mechanism for sustainable supply of products; in the agricultural sector formation of an advanced information system; administrative in food trade and technical obstacles loss; national certification organizations foreign in the states from accreditation transfer; aerial photomonitoring system work exit

the world scale food products deficiency getting stronger going in the circumstances country food products balance the following directions according to development to the goal according to

The composition of agricultural production based on this program change is set, according to which raw cotton until 2020 to grow 350 a thousand per ton step by step reduce set placed This in return 170 a thousand 500 hectares irrigated land from cotton will be released. Vegetables and potatoes, fodder crops, oil and other crops are grown in these fields. There are also gardens and vineyards will be done.

Few provided and low profitable population layers food products with provide mechanisms¹

It is known that market economy transition period country of the population the division into different strata according to income volumes is rapidly happening. Such in the situation in particular in Uzbekistan less provided population layers state by

¹IN THE GLOBALIZATION OF THE WORLD ECONOMY ENSURING FOOD SECURITY FROM OURSELVES. Economy sciences candidate scientific level get for present done dissertation AUTHOR ABSTRACT

social support, the first queue them foodwith products effective provision develop a mechanism exit is urgent remains. In this context, research work is underserved and low following the provision of food products to the income groups of the population mechanisms are proposed.

Optimization of cultivated areas and modern agricultural technologies as a result of its introduction, grain production increased by 16.4% in 2020, to increase its volume to 8 million 500 thousand tons, to grow potatoes 35 percent, vegetables 30 percent, fruit and grapes 21.5 percent, meat increase production by 26.2%, milk by 47.3%, eggs by 74.5%, fish production Increase by 2.5 times and export this type of food products size as famous amount increase attention received.

Also, construction and complete reconstruction of 274 modern refrigerating chambers and warehouses for storing more than 190 thousand tons of fruits and vegetables will be carried out.

To ensure food safety by the government of our republic worthy contribution adding coming all of subject work release activities more development purpose, organizational, economic and financial in terms of supporting is getting married. This the following in directions done is increased.

1. Village economy products work of producers right and interests practical to protect help to give
2. In order to create and develop multi-sectoral farms in order to increase food production, to implement projects related to vegetable growing, intensive horticulture, viticulture, animal husbandry, processing of agricultural products, and the organization of greenhouses. granting preferential loans by banks to economic entities within the framework of accepting special programs and implementing them.
3. food, in particular village economy products export increase and activity state by support and etc.

As in all regions of our country, in Namangan region, multi-branch farms produce agricultural products, perform their deep processing, carry out construction works, and provide various services to the rural population. is showing. This is finding its perspective.

Today, the number of such farms in the region is increasing. In particular, the Chashmai safed farm in Kosonsoy district is one of the multi-sectoral farms that have achieved steady progress and are developing as a result of the economic reforms

implemented by the head of state and our government. This economic activity covers various sectors such as breeding of livestock and agricultural products, processing of milk and meat products. As we know, the main effect of making profit is obtained from processing and then selling the products it produces. The Chashmai Safed farm pays a lot of attention to this, and by processing the milk grown in the farm, production of 12 types of dairy products such as cheese, yogurt, cream, butter, sour cream has been started. At the same time, the Kosonsoy cheese brand products produced here have permanent buyers in almost all markets of our country. Bread products produced at Ahmadkhan Haji Kosoniy farm in the district, as well as promising practices in other farms, can serve as an example for popularization throughout the country.

Many such farms occupy an important place in the economy of the district. As a result of this, last year the growth rate of gross agricultural products in Kosonsoy district was 108%.

Past in animal husbandry, Poultry and beekeeping development 71 projects have been implemented, with more than 200 million soums spent, As a result 100 ta new the work place was created. That's it with together, village the number of cattle on the farm is 40,000, including 13,600 cows head, sheep and goats 45.6 thousand heads, poultry 458.9 thousand heads, horses 285 a thousand heads and bees families 1808 know organize did

Food products work release expand and internal the marketto fill to the program according to district population cheap and good quality products with 42 thousand from agricultural products in order to further improve the supply tons of grain, 27.5 thousand tons of vegetables, 6.5 thousand tons of potatoes, 4 thousand tons grapes, 9.2 a thousand tons fruit was grown.

Also, other districts of the region contribute to the production of food products. In particular, the Korkam Nur Sahavat farm in Uychi district has launched a meat processing plant with an annual capacity of 15 tons. And in Norin district, the service points for receiving raw milk were launched by the Dildora farm

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Past years from experience come get out Noreen in the district 2019 in food safety provide for 34 ta project work released His to the performance 4 billion 580 million soum funds will be directed and that's it road with 145 ta new the workplace is created. animal husbandry, fishing, beekeeping, poultry farming develop, fruity

gardens, vineyards set up achieve new refrigerated establishment of warehouses, employment of meat processing shops drop off works planned. Such positive affairs of the region another districts too done is increasing.

1. Ensuring the stability of food safety in the Republic of Uzbekistan for, the first queue Agrarian in the field efficient and reasonable reforms continuous state support and its constant control should be under. Reforms in this area are the main food products part has been in grain farming take going from him high harvest to be taken provides and in the population consumption for remaining grain size year after year to increase take will come.

2. Few provided and low profitable population layers food products with of provision the following mechanisms current reach to the goal compatible with:

- addition the work places Create and subsidies separate (there is as an addition to their income); Supporting the development of small businesses support strengthen, population employment and new the work places organize to do to assist; consumption to increase the demand encouragement;

- preferential in prices food products centralized without distribution;
- in villages strong base, infrastructure and communications create ;

In conclusion, it can be said that food security is increasing all over the world today, which is gaining importance, the food of the population of our country necessary conditions to ensure food safety are created and clearly targeted measures done is increasing. Of these intended the goal country agriculture, which is one of the leading sectors of the economy, is stable develop, export potential increase and of Uzbekistan developed countries from the line strong place take over to provide directed.

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